

Is there scientific evidence to adjust haemoglobin by altitude to define anaemia?

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SUPPLEMENTARY FILE

Figure Supplementary 1 shows the areas under the curve (AUC) between anaemia (dependent variable) in adult women (n=253) defined with uncorrected haemoglobin with ferritin (independent variable). This shows an AUC of 0.6913 (sensitivity: 61.5% and specificity: 50.7%), while the AUC for anaemia diagnosed with corrected haemoglobin is 0.5494 (sensitivity: 50.0% and specificity: 48.4%), both models were controlled by inflammatory markers (albumin and interleukin-6), age and altitude of residence.

Figure Supplementary 1. Areas under the curve ROC. Left. Anaemia was defined with uncorrected haemoglobin (Hb < 12 mg/dl). Right. Anaemia was defined with corrected haemoglobin (Hb < 12 g/dl).

Correction was performed according WHO recommendation [1]. Data are obtained from a database including 475 adult men (n=253) and women (n=230) from Iquitos (130 m), Lima (150 m) and high-altitude (3280, 3800 and 4340 m) [2]. Analyses of these data are presented as **Figure S1** and **Table S1**. Data are from 230 adult women aged 18-75 years living in Iquitos (130 m), Lima (150 m), Huancayo (3280 m), Puno (3800 m) and Cerro de Pasco (4340 m). Independent variable was serum ferritin (ng/ml). Data were controlled by interleukin 6 and serum albumin.

Table Supplementary 1: Diagnostic performance of haemoglobin cut-off point to detect iron deficiency (ID) in adult women living at low altitudes (130 and 150 meter above sea level).

	Haemoglobin cutoff (g/dL)			
	<12	<13	<14	<15.6
Sensitivity (%)	25	63	83	96
Specificity (%)	76	47	31	4
Positive predictive value (%)	33	37	37	33
Negative predictive value (%)	67	72	79	67
Positive likelihood ratio	1.04	1.19	1.2	1

Negative likelihood ratio	0.99	0.79	0.55	1
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ID was defined when serum ferritin was < 15 ng/ml. Inflammatory status was controlled with serum interleukin 6 (IL6) and serum albumin levels.

References

1. World Health Organization. Haemoglobin concentrations for the diagnosis of anaemia and assessment of severity. 2011. <http://www.who.int/iris/handle/10665/85839>.
2. Gonzales, G.F.; Rubín de Celis, V.; Begazo, J.; Hinojosa, M.D.R.; Yucra, S.; Zevallos, A.; Tapia, V. Correcting the cut-off point of hemoglobin at high altitude favors misclassification of anemia, erythrocytosis and excessive erythrocytosis. *Am J Hematol.* 2018;93(1):E12–E16. doi:10.1002/ajh.24932